

CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF *SPILANTHES AOMELLA*

By V. G. GOKHALE AND B. V. BRIDE

Flowers of *Spilanthes Acmella* have been chemically examined. The pungent principle has been shown to be identical with spilanthol which was first isolated by Gerber from *Spilanthes Oleracea*.

Spilanthol was isolated from *Spilanthes Oleracea* (N.O. *Compositae*) or the American para cross by Gerber (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1903, 141, 270). Spilanthol has been shown to be the isobutyl amide of decadienoic acid [Asano and Asahina, *J. Pharm. Soc. (Japan)*, 1920, No. 460, 503 ; 1922, 85 ; Asano and Kanematsu, *Ber.*, 1932, 65B, 1602].

The Indian variety, *Spilanthes Acmella*, does not appear to have been chemically examined. The flower head of *S. Acmella* has a hot burning taste and is a popular remedy for children who stammer. Recently we have found that the flower or the extract of the flowers is a powerful mosquito larvicide.

The flowers have been extracted successively with different solvents and it has been found that ether extracts the pungent principle effectively. The ether extract after removal of the solvent is treated with 60 % alcohol when an orange-coloured gum (A) separates. This gum does not possess the characteristic pungent taste, nor does it give any crystalline substance. It is therefore hydrolysed by alcoholic potash and the unsaponifiable matter separated. The resulting semi-solid material is crystallised several times from alcohol and finally from ethyl acetate when a sterol, m.p. 184-85°, is obtained. Gerber (*loc. cit.*) has isolated a sterol, m.p. 178° from *Spilanthes Oleracea*. The mother-liquors give a white solid melting indefinitely between 75° and 81° but no homogeneous substance could be isolated.

On removal of alcohol from the extract a dark coloured liquid (B) is obtained from which spilanthol has been isolated.

The flowers do not give an essential oil in any appreciable quantity on steam distillation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The dry flower heads gave 8 % ash which consisted of potassium nitrate and small quantities of calcium and magnesium with traces of iron. Positive tests for phosphate, chloride and sulphate were also obtained. The flower heads did not give any test for alkaloids when extracted with Prolious fluid.

50 G. of the flowering heads were extracted successively with various solvents (Table I.)

The water extract did not reduce Fehling's solution but on boiling with dilute hydrochloric acid the solution readily reduced it thus showing the presence of polysaccharides.

3 Kg. of the flowering heads of the plant were extracted by cold percolation with ether. The ether extract was dried over magnesium sulphate and ether removed. The residue was a dark green viscous oil (35 g.). This extract was then extracted with 60%

TABLE I

Solvent.	% Wt. of extract.	Nature of extract.
Petrol (b.p. 40-60°)	0.57	Waxy material
Ether sulphuric	0.26	Dark green pungent liquid
Chloroform	0.05	Slightly pungent dark green liquid
Alcohol	0.6	" " " " "
Water	0.4	Sweet thick syrup

alcohol (80 c.c.) 3 times. The residue was an orange-coloured viscous mass (A) (15 g.) and had no pungent taste. The alcohol from the alcoholic extract was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was taken up in ether, the ether extract dried and ether removed. The residue (18 g.) (B) was a dark green oil and had pungent taste.

Examination of (A).—The substance was treated with a solution of potassium hydroxide (15 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) and benzene (10 c.c.) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 12 hours. The benzene and most of the alcohol were removed. The residue was suspended in a large quantity of water and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried and ether removed. The residue was a waxy yellow solid. It was crystallised several times from alcohol and finally from ethyl acetate when it melted at 184-85°. It gave all the colour reactions of a sterol. The mother-liquors on treatment with digitonin solution gave a further quantity of sterol on decomposition of the digitonide.

The alkaline solution on removal of the unsaponifiable matter gave a dark coloured liquid. This was crystallised several times from alcohol when a small quantity of an acid, m.p. 75-81°, was obtained but the quantity was too small for further investigation.

Examination of (B): Identification of Spilanthol.—The alcohol extract (B) was taken up in ether, washed and dried over magnesium sulphate and ether was removed. The residue was distilled under 20 mm. pressure. The main fraction (10 g.) (C) distilled over at 220-225° as a pale yellow liquid leaving a black residue (5 g.) which could not be purified. The distillate (C) had a strong tingling taste when placed on the tongue. It contained nitrogen and absorbed bromine.

Maleic Anhydride Addition product of the liquid (C).—The liquid (5 g.) and maleic anhydride (5 g.) were dissolved in toluene (25 c.c.) and refluxed for 3 hours. Water (25 c.c.) was then added and the boiling was continued for another 1 hour. It was then cooled and the toluene layer was separated and washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution. The sodium salt of the adduct crystallised out. It was suspended in benzene and decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was removed, washed with water, dried and benzene removed when a crystalline solid, m.p. 168-69°, was obtained. This is identical with the m.p. of the maleic anhydride adduct of the spilanthol isolated from *Spilanthes Oleracea* (Asano and Kanematsu, *loc. cit.*).

Oxidation of Spilanthol.—Spilanthol (5 g.) was dissolved in acetone (50 c.c.) and powdered potassium permanganate (30 g.) was added in small lots. A vigorous reaction

occurred and heat was developed. On keeping overnight the acetone was recovered on a water-bath. The residue was suspended in water and sulphur dioxide was passed in till all the manganese dioxide dissolved. A small quantity of a white gum separated which was filtered off. The filtrate was extracted with ether several times and the ether extract was dried and ether removed. The residue on washing with a little benzene gave succinic acid, m.p. 184° (mixed m.p.). Asano and Kanematsu (*loc. cit.*) obtained formic, succinic and butyric acids on ozonolysis of spilanthol.

MAHARAJA PRATAPSINH CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SIR PARASHURAMBHAU COLLEGE,
POONA.

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